

WorldFAIR WP08 SALURBAL

Organization	GO FAIR
Created by	ANA ORTIGOZA (anitaortigoza2@gmail.com)
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Project Phase	never
Project Tags	Type: FIP
Created at	10 Oct 2022

I. About

Questions

No questions

II. Declare your FAIR Implementation Community

Questions

1

Select your FAIR Implementation Community

SALURBAL-data-portal

This is a community that is designing and developing a data platform for making SALURBAL data available to researchers working within the project. It is also thought that the data platform can be used by external researchers and stakeholders once the project is ended.

http://purl.org/np/RAgXlupFh_pDjajQhiU4OegxIF8zANt41NMBIaINKBtvs#SALURBAL-portal

2

Who is the Community Data Steward?

✓ 0000-0001-8100-422

3

Specify the start date for the validity of the FIP

✓ 2022-11-01

4

Specify the end date for the validity of the FIP

✓ 2050-12-31

III. Declarations for Findability

Questions

1

Declaration F1 Metadata: What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

DOI | Digital Object Identifier

The digital object identifier (DOI) system originated in a joint initiative of three trade associations in the publishing industry (International Publishers Association; International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers; Association of American Publishers). The system was announced at the Frankfurt Book Fair 1997. The International DOI Foundation (IDF) was created to develop and manage the DOI system, also in 1997. The DOI system was adopted as International Standard ISO 26324 in 2012. The DOI system implements the Handle System and adds a number of new features. The DOI system provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. The DOI system is designed to work over the Internet. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object, or information about it, can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata. The DOI system enables the construction of automated services and transactions. Applications of the DOI system include but are not limited to managing information and documentation location and access; managing metadata; facilitating electronic transactions; persistent unique identification of any form of any data; and commercial and non-commercial transactions. The content of an object associated with a DOI name is described unambiguously by DOI metadata, based on a structured extensible data model that enables the object to be associated with metadata of

any desired degree of precision and granularity to support description and services. The data model supports interoperability between DOI applications. The scope of the DOI system is not defined by reference to the type of content (format, etc.) of the referent, but by reference to the functionalities it provides and the context of use. The DOI system provides, within networks of DOI applications, for unique identification, persistence, resolution, metadata and semantic interoperability.

http://purl.org/np/RAnAWGdel_1GGmDAqv-vZjby5Xqbl2ZujNz1vgwK_6cRI#DOI

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ c. Is planned to be used in the future

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- ✓ DOI will be assigned to each metadata and data once the data portal is finished

1.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

SALURBAL FAIR strategy

This is the strategy SALURBAL is developing to implement FAIR principles into the data portal

http://purl.org/np/RAOM5tzZC935CEXgIj_SKHQCMrSiAGDVQOM7y_64XKcQI#SALURBAL-FAIR

1.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ b. Currently in use, but is planned to be replaced in the future

1.b.1.b.2.b.1

Select the replacement FAIR Enabling Resource

Inter university Consortium for Political and Social Research

An international consortium of more than 750 academic institutions and research organizations, that hosts 21 specialized collections of data. ICPSR acts as a global leader in data stewardship and provides training in data access, curation, and methods of analysis for the social science research community

http://purl.org/np/RA0s9-5yUhXz-5ZfM3GLUHpqOqrpNQv1QNtR_Fa0rYTfM#ICPSR

1.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration

- ✓ The SALURBAL data portal and its FAIR implementation strategy is a transition for service considered while SALURBAL researchers are still in need of the use of data within the project. Once the project ends, the data will migrate to ICPSR service following all its FAIR requirements

2

Declaration F1 Data: What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for datasets?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

SALURBAL FAIR strategy

This is the strategy SALURBAL is developing to implement FAIR principles into the data portal

http://purl.org/np/RAOM5tzZC935CEXgJJ_SKHQCMrSiAGDVQQM7y_64XKcQI#SALURBAL-FAIR

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ b. Currently in use, but is planned to be replaced in the future

2.b.1.a.2.b.1

Select the replacement FAIR Enabling Resource

DOI | Digital Object Identifier

The digital object identifier (DOI) system originated in a joint initiative of three trade associations in the publishing industry (International Publishers Association; International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers; Association of American Publishers). The system was announced at the Frankfurt Book Fair 1997. The International DOI Foundation (IDF) was created to develop and manage the DOI system, also in 1997. The DOI system was adopted as International Standard ISO 26324 in 2012. The DOI system implements the Handle System and adds a number of new features. The DOI system provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. The DOI system is designed to work over the Internet. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object, or information about it, can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata. The DOI system enables the construction of automated services and transactions. Applications of

the DOI system include but are not limited to managing information and documentation location and access; managing metadata; facilitating electronic transactions; persistent unique identification of any form of any data; and commercial and non-commercial transactions. The content of an object associated with a DOI name is described unambiguously by DOI metadata, based on a structured extensible data model that enables the object to be associated with metadata of any desired degree of precision and granularity to support description and services. The data model supports interoperability between DOI applications. The scope of the DOI system is not defined by reference to the type of content (format, etc.) of the referent, but by reference to the functionalities it provides and the context of use. The DOI system provides, within networks of DOI applications, for unique identification, persistence, resolution, metadata and semantic interoperability.

http://purl.org/np/RAnAWGdel_1GGmDAqv-vZjby5XqbL2ZujNz1vgwK_6cRI#DOI

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- ✓ Currently each variable has a unique identifier which we term var_name, but once the data will be at ICPSR a DOI will be assigned for each dataset and variable

3

Declaration F2: What metadata schema do you use for findability?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

SALURBAL FAIR strategy

This is the strategy SALURBAL is developing to implement FAIR principles into the data portal

http://purl.org/np/RAOM5tzZC935CEXgJl_SKHQCmrSiAGDVOQM7y_64XKcQI#SALURBAL-FAIR

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ b. Currently in use, but is planned to be replaced in the future

3.b.1.a.2.b.1

Select the replacement FAIR Enabling Resource

DDI-Codebook|Data Documentation Initiative - Codebook

DDI-Codebook is a more light-weight version of the standard, intended primarily to document simple survey data. Originally DTD-based, DDI-C is also available as an XML Schema.

http://purl.org/np/RAh3tbu1Z7qqVD6Ool77Mp6FjoJk7scRTD_-I3ufWZpng#DDI-Codebook

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- ✓ In the development of the data portal, it appear the need for a codebook renovation as date cannot be machine actionable with the codebooks available. New codebooks consider the following categories Identifiers: columns responsible for linkage of data and metadata. var_name is our workhorse identifier which links things at the variable-level - it should not contain strata information Categorization: columns responsible for grouping variables into user friendly domains and subdomains. Details: research related variables details, this will be useful for users who want to reuse our data/codebooks. Internal: internal project related metadata (file directories and access status).

4

Declaration F3: What is the schema that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?

- ✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

5

Declaration F4 Metadata: Which service do you use to publish your metadata records?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

5.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

5.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

SALURBAL FAIR strategy

This is the strategy SALURBAL is developing to implement FAIR principles into the data portal

http://purl.org/np/RAOM5tzZC935CEXgIj_SKHQCmrSiAGDVOQM7y_64XKcOI#SALURBAL-FAIR

5.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ c. Is planned to be used in the future

5.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

6

Declaration F4 Datasets: Which service do you use to publish your datasets?

✔ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

6.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

6.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

SALURBAL FAIR strategy

This is the strategy SALURBAL is developing to implement FAIR principles into the data portal

http://purl.org/np/RAOM5tzZC935CEXgIj_SKHQcmrSiAGDVQQM7y_64XKcQI#SALURBAL-FAIR

6.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✔ c. Is planned to be used in the future

6.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

IV. Declarations for Accessibility

Questions

1

Declaration A1.1 Metadata: Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

SALURBAL FAIR strategy

This is the strategy SALURBAL is developing to implement FAIR principles into the data portal

http://purl.org/np/RAOM5tzZC935CEXgJJ_SKHQCMrSiAGDVQOM7y_64XKcQI#SALURBAL-FAIR

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ c. Is planned to be used in the future

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✓ Currently standardized communication protocols for metadata and data are under renovation We use HTTPS to facilitate data transfer. There are two main ways for users to download data: 1) each variable's web page contains download links for data and associated metadata 2) users and create a custom data extract on the data portal and have the data/metadata operationalied into a analytical bundle that is then emailed to them.

2

Declaration A1.1 Datasets: Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

SALURBAL FAIR strategy

This is the strategy SALURBAL is developing to implement FAIR principles into the data portal

http://purl.org/np/RAOM5tzZC935CEXgJJ_SKHQCmrSiAGDVQOM7y_64XKcQI#SALURBAL-FAIR

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ c. Is planned to be used in the future

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3

Declaration A1.2 Metadata: Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

SALURBAL FAIR strategy

This is the strategy SALURBAL is developing to implement FAIR principles into the data portal

http://purl.org/np/RAOM5tzZC935CEXgIj_SKHQcmrSiAGDVQOM7y_64XKcQI#SALURBAL-FAIR

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ c. Is planned to be used in the future

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- ✓ We deploy the data portal via the Azure Static Web Application Service. This service has built in authentication via OAuth integrating with GitHub or Outlook for handle user authentication. We then write authorisation logic as need in our front-end Next.js application to control information flow. Although this mechanism was developed, we do use it to primarily track user behavior. SALURBAL data is stored on an private encrypted server hosted by Drexel University. Data items that which have contractual restrictions remain on this private encrypted server. Data items that are open to the public are then stored within Azure Blob Storage with anonymously access (anyone can have access to them).

4

Declaration A1.2 Datasets: Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for datasets?

- ✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

5

Declaration A2: What metadata preservation policy do you use?

- ✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

V. Declarations for Interoperability

Questions

1

Declaration I1 Metadata: What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

SALURBAL FAIR strategy

This is the strategy SALURBAL is developing to implement FAIR principles into the data portal

http://purl.org/np/RAOM5tzZC935CEXgJJ_SKHQCmrSiAGDVQQM7y_64XKcQI#SALURBAL-FAIR

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ c. Is planned to be used in the future

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✓ Data and metadata is stored in Azure Blob Storage in both CSV form as well as JSON format. JSON is highly interoperable as a REST API for web applications; for example our data portal pulls from this to provide analytics/visualizations. CSV is a common data sharing format in the epi field; any download links or downloaded data from our data portal comes in CSV format as it is more human friendly.

2

Declaration I1 Datasets: What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?

✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

3

Declaration I2 Metadata: What structured vocabulary do you use to annotate your metadata records?

✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

4

Declaration I2 Datasets: What structured vocabulary do you use to encode your datasets

✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

5

Declaration I3 Metadata: What semantic model do you use for your metadata records?

✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

6

Declaration I3 Datasets: What semantic model do you use for your datasets?

- ✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

VI. Declarations for Reusability

Questions

1

Declaration R1.1 Metadata: Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

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http://purl.org/np/RAQ_sGdY_Qc7l1O_zmn4nr-pMBOxKU04Ur9s998rS6Fc#CC-BY-4.0

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ c. Is planned to be used in the future

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

2

Declaration R1.1 Datasets: Which usage license do you use for your datasets?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

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http://purl.org/np/RAQ_sGdY_Qc7l1O_zmn4nr-pMBOxKU04Ur9s998rS6Fc#CC-BY-4.0

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ c. Is planned to be used in the future

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

3

Declaration R1.2 Metadata: What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?

- ✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

4

Declaration R1.2 Datasets: What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?

- ✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

5

Declaration R1.3: Your community uses this FAIR Implementation Profile to link to domain-relevant community standards.

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

VII. Register a new resource as a nanopublication

Questions

No questions